

Thermoosmosis Across Cellulose Acetate and Cellulose Nitrate Membranes

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Thermoosmosis of water across cellulose acetate and nitrate membranes have been studied at a number of mean temperatures, and results interpreted in terms of modification of structure of water in the membrane phase in relation to that in bulk water. A few preliminary observations on thermoosmosis of some electrolyte solutions have also been reported.

REPORTS have appeared in recent literature¹⁻³ regarding "less mobile" water in contact with cellulosic membranes, in particular cellulose acetate. It has been also postulated^{4,5} that an effective salt-exclusion by the latter in reverse osmosis results from such changes (from bulk water) in the structure of water in the membrane phase. It is worth noting in this context that thermoosmotic studies of water may also lead to important information as to the nature of interactions of water with the membrane matrix causing modification of structure of water in the latter, and may thus be useful in elucidating the mechanism of water-transport through membranes of various degrees of hydrophilicity and charge. However, a quick survey of literature reveals that the phenomenon of thermoosmosis of liquids has been a subject of controversy at both the theoretical and experimental levels⁶. An agreement between theoretical predictions and experimental results is also lacking in some cases. This has been appropriately expressed by Haase⁷ who maintained that only a few, and in part, questionable observations on thermoosmosis in liquid systems were extant. In this background, an attempt has been made here to study the thermoosmosis of water across cellulose acetate (2.5 acetate) and nitrate membranes, and interpret the results in terms of the theories of irreversible thermodynamics. Some preliminary observations on thermoosmosis of electrolytes across cellulose acetate have also been reported, and the data fitted to formulations of a simplified model (based on non-equilibrium thermodynamics), recently developed and put to test for thermoosmosis across glass membranes⁸, in order to derive the corresponding electrolytic heats of transport.

Theoretical :

In thermoosmosis experiments, a membrane separates two portions of a liquid in which intensive variables have uniform values, but each portion is not in thermodynamic equilibrium with the other. The temperature gradient, considered linear, is confined to the membrane thickness only and the latter is a seat of thermal diffusion. All

gradients in temperature and chemical potential (if any) are supposed to be confined to the membrane phase (which may be attained by keeping each bulk phase thoroughly mixed). A detailed discussion of the theory has already been given⁶, and an outline is sketched below.

The following linear phenomenological equations between fluxes and forces refer to the membrane phase,

$$J_q = L_{qq}X_q + L_{qw}X_w \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

$$J_w = L_{wq}X_q + L_{ww}X_w \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

where J_q and J_w are the flux densities (defined relative to $J_{membrane}=0$) of heat and water, respectively, and X_q and X_w the corresponding thermodynamic driving forces. L_{qq} and L_{ww} are the direct phenomenological coefficients for the independent processes of thermal conduction and diffusion through the membrane, while L_{qw} and L_{wq} are the "cross-effect" coefficients representing coupling between the two flows in the membrane phase. The fluxes and forces are so chosen as to satisfy the requirements of Onsager Reciprocity Relation (O. R. R.) between the cross-effect coefficients, namely the equality $L_{qw}=L_{wq}$ in the present case.

For thermoosmosis of water, the forces are defined as,

$$X_q = - \frac{1}{T} \cdot \frac{dT}{dx} \quad \dots \quad (3)$$

$$X_w = - \frac{RT}{p} \cdot \frac{dp}{dx} \quad \dots \quad (4)$$

where p is the hydrostatic pressure due to bulk migration of water through the membrane. For an isothermal situation, ($X_q=0$), it follows from eqs. 1 and 2,

$$J_q = J_w \cdot \frac{L_{qw}}{L_{ww}} \quad \dots \quad (5)$$

Another important parameter, heat of transport ($\overset{\Delta}{Q}_w$), which is the amount of heat absorbed per mole of a diffusing substance from the region it leaves and released in the region it moves into,

under isothermal conditions (and with migration of no other component in a polycomponent system), may now be introduced from eq. 5, namely,

$$\left(\frac{J_q}{J_w}\right)_{x_a=0} = \frac{L_{qw}}{L_{ww}} = \hat{Q}_w \quad \dots (6)$$

where \hat{Q}_w is the heat of transport of water. \hat{Q}_w is sensitive to interactions of water with the membrane^{9,6}.

At the steady state, $J_w=0$, and by using O.R.R., we obtain from eq. 2

$$\left(\frac{X_w}{X_q}\right)_{st} = -\frac{L_{wq}}{L_{ww}} = -\frac{L_{qw}}{L_{ww}} = -\hat{Q}_w \quad \dots (7)$$

(from eq. 6)

the subscript 'st' denoting the steady state. On substitution of eqs. 3 and 4 in eq. 7, one obtains,

$$\hat{Q}_w = -\frac{RT^2}{p} \cdot \frac{dp}{dT} \quad \dots (8), \text{ and by using the}$$

relation, $p = \frac{RT}{\bar{V}}$, we get

$$\hat{Q}_w = -\bar{V} \cdot T \left(\frac{dp}{dT}\right)_{st} \quad \dots (9)$$

where \bar{V} is the molar volume of water and T the mean temperature and $\left(\frac{dp}{dT}\right)_{st}$ refers to the steady state value across the membrane. Eq. 9 has been used to obtain \hat{Q}_w of water across the membranes investigated in the present case.

For thermoosmosis of electrolytes, simplifications are to be made owing to the inherent complications of transport in electrolyte-solvent systems under temperature gradients. Recently, Sanyal and Mukherjee³ have developed an approximate frame-work, based on irreversible thermodynamics, to deal with cases of thermoosmosis of electrolytes across membranes subjected to zero initial osmotic pressure difference. For such cases it was shown possible to disregard the solvent contribution to the overall heat of transport, and hence the resultant simplification. The equation giving the heat of transport of the electrolyte, \hat{Q} , reads,

$$\hat{Q} = \nu RT^2 \sigma \left(1 + \frac{d \ln \gamma_{\pm}}{d \ln m}\right) - \bar{V} \cdot T \cdot \left(\frac{dp}{dT}\right)_{st} \quad \dots (10)$$

where $\nu = \nu_1 + \nu_2$ = total number of ions produced on complete dissociation of one mole of electrolyte, γ_{\pm} is the mean ionic activity coefficient, m the mean ionic molality and σ the Soret coefficient of the solute; σ is given by the equation, $\sigma = -\left(\frac{d \ln m}{dT}\right)_{st}$. Obviously, if m_o and m_w are the cold- and warm-side molal concentrations of the electrolyte at the steady state and m the initial uniform molality throughout, then,

$$\sigma = -\left(\frac{d \ln m}{dT}\right)_{st} = -\frac{1}{m} \cdot \left(\frac{dm}{dT}\right)_{st} = -\frac{1}{m} \cdot \frac{\Delta m}{\Delta T} \quad \dots (11)$$

where ΔT is the temperature difference and $\Delta m = m_o - m_w$.

For dilute solutions, the variation of the mean ionic activity coefficient with molality may be ignored by setting $\frac{d \ln \gamma_{\pm}}{d \ln m} \simeq 0$, and eq. 10 reduces to

$$\hat{Q} = \nu RT^2 \sigma - \bar{V} T \left(\frac{dp}{dT}\right)_{st} \quad \dots (12)$$

Experimental

Apparatus :

Thermoosmotic cell : The cell is mounted in a horizontal position and is in three parts, the membrane assembly forming the central section being sandwiched in horizontal position between the upper and lower solution chambers. Each of the latter is cut in a perspex block in a circular section of 3 cm diam. and 0.5 cm thickness. The bottom of each half-cell is closed by a thin mylar sheet kept in position by being pressed against a brass plate (2 mm thick), the outer face of which forms the lower inside wall of a brass water jacket welded to the former. The plate fits in a well-cut groove in the perspex block. Water from two thermostats, maintained at different temperatures, is circulated by means of Tulu water circulating pumps through these upper and lower water jackets. The membrane is held between two annular perspex discs of thickness 1 mm each and provided with 'O'-ring arrangements. The entire cell with its three parts is assembled together by a number of brass nuts and bolts screwed through the outer peripheral parts of the upper and lower brass plates. A number of channels (eight in number) ending into each half cell are cut through the perspex block and one Ag/AgCl/Cl⁻ electrode with a saltbridge, two copper-constantan thermocouple junctions, two face-to-face (across diameter of the central circular groove) platinum conductivity electrodes, along with two face-to-face 1 mm inside diam. glass capillary tubes are held fixed in these channels. The glass tubes (both ends) emerging from each half-cell through the block are bent at right angles at a distance of 3 mm from the end of the perspex block. The portions of the glass tubes outside the block are covered with glass wool to insulate the same from the ambient temperature fluctuations.

Preparation of membranes : Cellulose acetate and cellulose nitrate membranes were prepared by dissolving 4 g of materials in 50 ml of acetone and stirring well until a clear viscous solution was obtained, and then casting the solution on glass plates and allowing the solvent to evaporate slowly, usually at room temperature, in an atmosphere nearly saturated with acetone vapour.

Materials and methods :

The water used in the thermoosmotic experiments was double distilled water of conductivity less than 0.5 μ mho cm⁻¹, while the electrolytes NaCl, MgSO₄ and CuSO₄ were of AnalaR[®](B.D.H.)

grade. The solutions were carefully degassed at pump before use and the initial mean concentrations determined interferometrically.

Before the start of an actual run, the cell mounted in a horizontal position was filled with the liquid (water or solution), taking care to exclude air bubbles, and water from two thermostats was circulated through the upper and lower water jackets to record uniform (but different) temperatures in the two half-cells. The thermoosmotic flow of water through the membranes was ascertained by noting the rate of development of pressure-head difference between the glass tubes emerging from the top and bottom half-cells. Such pressure-head differences across the membrane reaching constant values indicate the attainment of the steady state in the system. The heat of transport, \hat{Q}_w , of the water at the appropriate mean temperatures was then obtained by using eq. 9. The experiment was repeated at a number of other mean temperatures.

For the electrolytes, the solution concentrations and their changes were periodically monitored by recording (for NaCl) the changes of electrodes potentials of the Ag/AgCl/Cl⁻ electrode (by coupling the latter through a salt bridge with a calomel electrode and recording the e.m.f. of the cell) and also by measuring the conductivity as a function of time, of the solution in each half-cell. The attainment of the steady state, $\sum_j J_j = 0$, was indicated by the concentration differences across the membrane (in addition to the pressure-head differences) registering constant values independent of time. The heat of transport of the electrolyte concerned was then obtained by referring to eq. 10. The solutions studied were aqueous solutions of NaCl, MgSO₄ or CuSO₄, each with a mean concentration of 0.05 m.

Results and Discussion

The heat of transport values of water across cellulose acetate and nitrate membranes at a series of mean temperatures, as obtained with the aid of eq. 9 (after having made corrections in the record of pressure-heads due to unequal volume expansion in the two half-cells), have been recorded in Tables 1 and 2, respectively. The values for both the

TABLE 2—HEAT OF TRANSPORT OF WATER AT DIFFERENT MEAN TEMPERATURES (USING CELLULOSE NITRATE MEMBRANE)

Mean temp. °C	\hat{Q}_w /J. mol ⁻¹
22.5	0.415
25.3	0.384
27.2	0.360
28.9	0.314
30.0	0.187
32.2	0.031
33.1	-0.064
33.9	-0.150
34.9	-0.180
37.8	-0.224
40.3	-0.236

membranes are found to be negative at temperatures above about 30°, and positive below this down to 22.5°, the lowest temperature studied. A negative value of \hat{Q}_w corresponds to bulk migration towards the hot end (vide. eq. 9) and is associated with liberation of heat behind the diffusing entity (i. e., water) and an absorption ahead in course of diffusional transport through the membrane (vide, definition of \hat{Q}_w given earlier). Inasmuch \hat{Q}_w manifests the difference in degree of ordering between water in the bulk and that in contact with the membrane matrix, the negative values find an interpretation in terms of promotion of water structure in the membrane phase, particularly so with cellulose acetate (having only 0.5 unit of free hydroxyl per glucose unit of the polymer), through what is known as "hydrophobic hydration"¹². On this basis, a rise in mean temperature should cause an increase in the negative magnitude of \hat{Q}_w in view of a corresponding increase in the kinetic energy (and hence "disorder") of water molecules in the bulk, especially in relation to that of water molecules in contact with the stationary (and largely hydrophobic) cellulose acetate. Experimental results agree with this prediction. The presence of nitro-groups (in place of acetyl) in cellulose nitrate tends to reduce its hydrophobic character and consequently the extent of "structure promotion" in the membrane, so that the corresponding \hat{Q}_w should be rendered less negative at a given mean temperature. This also finds a support from the experimental results (vide Tables 1 and 2). An examination of the data reveals a reversal of sign of \hat{Q}_w in the temperature range 30-33° for both the membranes suggesting a zero heat of transport at some intermediate temperature. It is worth noting in this context that the specific heat of water also exhibits a minimum in this range of temperature so that the promotion of structure of water (by, for instance, cellulose acetate) is rendered difficult in the same range (by keeping in view the fact that the abnormally high specific heat of water is due to the destruction of intermolecular hydrogen bonds on raising the temperature and the minimum specific heat may imply the lowest degree of

TABLE 1—HEAT OF TRANSPORT OF WATER AT DIFFERENT MEAN TEMPERATURES (USING CELLULOSE ACETATE MEMBRANE)

Mean temp. °C	\hat{Q}_w /J. mol ⁻¹
23.2	0.356
24.9	0.256
27.0	0.200
30.5	0.033
32.5	-0.05
33.3	-0.123
34.2	-0.197
35.0	-0.208
36.7	-0.217
37.5	-0.250
38.9	-0.267
42.0	-0.308

TABLE 3—HEAT OF TRANSPORT OF ELECTROLYTES IN THE CELLULOSE ACETATE MEMBRANE

Aqueous solution at 0.05 M	Mean temp. °C	$10^3(C_o - C_w)/m$ at the steady state	Soret coefficient/deg ⁻¹ $10^3 \sigma = 10^3 \left(\frac{d \ln m}{dT} \right)_{st}$	$\left(1 + \frac{d \ln \gamma_{\pm}}{d \ln m} \right)_{25^\circ}$ from literature ^{1,4} (B)	$\bar{V} \cdot T \left(\frac{d p}{dT} \right)_{st}$ J. mol ⁻¹	$\frac{\Delta Q_w}{J. mol^{-1}} = \nu BRT^2 \sigma - \bar{V} T \left(\frac{d p}{dT} \right)_{st}$
NaCl ($\nu = 2$)	22.2	0.14	1.27	0.86	0.41	1581
MgSO ₄ ($\nu = 2$)	24.7	0.56	2.0	0.56	0.26	1650
CuSO ₄ ($\nu = 2$)	22.9	0.45	3.1	0.42	0.38	1894

structure). One may, therefore, expect a very low ΔQ_w in this range and indeed the experimental results are in agreement. The observation that the "zero- ΔQ_w " temperature in cellulose nitrate appears to be somewhat higher than the acetate value may again be attributed to the greater hydrophilic character of the former.

It, however, becomes difficult to explain the positive values of the heat of transport (i.e., migration to the colder parts) by arguing in these lines and possible other factors such as heat of solution of water in the membrane phase will have to be taken into consideration to determine the direction of net migration. Because of very incomplete state, in a quantitative sense, of understanding of the mechanism of water transport through these membranes and also the uncertainty as to the mode of transport of water through, for instance, cellulose acetate membrane (being whether entirely diffusional, or partly pore flow¹³), a completely satisfactory explanation of such heats of transport values will have to wait for some time to come.

Lastly, the results for the electrolytes are incorporated in Table 3. The values of the thermodynamic factor, $\left(1 + \frac{d \ln \gamma_{\pm}}{d \ln m} \right)_x$, at 25° for the

0.05M solutions investigated have been noted from the literature¹⁴ and assumed unchanged with mean temperature in the range covered (22-25°). The pressure-head differences as well as the hot- and cold-side concentrations at the steady state have been measured as already indicated, and use is made of eq. 10 to obtain the corresponding electrolytic heats of transport. For all the solutions studied the electrolyte was found to concentrate on the cooler side of the membrane.

The heat of transport values (column 7, table 3) are seen to increase with molecular weight of the salts and also with valency of the constituent ions. Whereas the latter arises primarily from a higher ionic potential (charge to radius ratio) of Mg²⁺, Cu²⁺ and SO₄²⁻ as compared to that of Na⁺ and Cl⁻, in the hydrated state (which promotes, through long range interactions, structure of water in, for instance, B and C layers of Frank and Wen's zone model¹⁰ later perfected by Némethy and Scheraga¹¹ of aqueous electrolyte solutions and thereby raises ΔQ_w), the former simple direct trend with the molecular weight is in contrast with the behaviour of the alkali metal chlorides in aqueous solutions⁹.

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